

Towards a 100% Renewable Uruguay: Challenges and Opportunities in the Energy Transition

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Executive Summary

Uruguay is on path toward a 100% renewable energy system, achieving 91% renewable electricity generation in 2022. This report analyzes the challenges and opportunities of this transition in the face of growing energy demand and the challenges posed by climate variability. Through the OSeMOSYS model, three scenarios were evaluated: Tendential (TR), Water Scarcity Scenario (WS), and Water Scarcity + Grid-Connected Batteries (WS+GCB), focusing on the evolution of the energy matrix and the resilience of the system in response to reduced water resources.

The results show that wind energy emerges as the primary source in scenarios with lower hydroelectric generation. Grid-connected batteries, incorporated in the (WS+GCB) scenario, play a crucial role in stabilizing the electricity supply during demand peaks, reducing reliance on fossil fuels and CO₂ emissions. However, these solutions require significant investments, increasing long-term accumulated costs.

Uruguay has the opportunity to lead the energy transition with a sustainable and resilient system. It will be essential to diversify the energy matrix, adopt storage technologies, and establish policies that promote flexibility and reduce dependence on fossil resources in the near future.

Introduction

Climate change and the increase in greenhouse gas emissions have accelerated the need for a sustainable energy transition. In this context, as indicated by (Taibi et al., 2018), variable renewable energies, such as solar photovoltaic and wind, have taken on a key role due to their low carbon footprint compared to fossil sources.

In the case of Uruguay, the country has positioned itself as a leader in this transition, achieving a 56% renewable energy supply and 91% renewable electricity generation in 2022 (MIEM, 2022). However, the growing penetration of variable sources poses challenges to system stability due to resource intermittency and the need for operational flexibility.

The management of storage, the optimization of baseload generation, and the adaptation of demand are critical factors to sustaining a 100% renewable system. This raises key questions: Is a fully renewable electrical system viable in Uruguay? How would the system respond to a reduction in the availability of water resources? This study aims to evaluate these aspects and provide technical evidence on the resilience and sustainability of Uruguay's electrical system.

Methodology

For the calibration of the base model, updated energy data from the (Balance Energético Nacional, 2023) were used, covering the period 2021-2023. These data include resource acquisition, installed capacity, and energy consumption disaggregated by sector, providing a solid foundation for representing the energy system and its recent evolution.

The tool used for this study was **OSeMOSYS**. OSeMOSYS is an open-source modeling system designed for energy planning and integrated long-term assessment. It has been applied to the development of energy models at various scales. OSeMOSYS flexibility allows for the representation of both detailed energy systems and configurations that integrate multiple resources (OSeMOSYS, 2025).

Three scenarios were evaluated: the **Tendential Scenario (TR)**, the **Water Scarcity Scenario (WS)**, and the **Water Scarcity + Grid-Connected Batteries Scenario (WS+GCB)**. Figure 1 presents a summary of the main characteristics of these scenarios:

- The **TR** Scenario represents Uruguay's energy system in its current state and how it would behave over the years, using historical data from the 2021-2023 period. This allows for an analysis of the performance of various technologies.
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- The **WS** Scenario simulates a reduction in the availability of water resources for hydropower generation, with the objective of evaluating how the system can meet demand using other energy sources available in the country.
 - The **WS+GCB** Scenario aims to determine the behavior of the electrical system under water scarcity conditions while incorporating large-scale energy storage. The operation of batteries is considered to absorb excess generation during periods of high renewable availability and to inject it during deficit periods, optimizing the management of supply and demand.

Figure 1. Diagram of modeled scenarios.

Results

Figure 2 shows that the installed capacity in the three scenarios remains relatively constant until 2030 but experiences a significant increase starting in 2040, especially in the WS and WS+GCB scenarios, where it doubles by 2050. This increase is driven by the expansion of wind generation, which becomes the dominant technology due to its competitiveness and abundant resources, while hydroelectric generation remains constant due to potential limitations. It is important to highlight that the relative constancy in installed capacity until 2030 is influenced by the oversizing of plants installed in the country, which allowed demand to be met without significant expansions during that period. In the WS+GCB scenario, the share of fossil technologies decreases significantly, being partially replaced by batteries starting in 2040. To make these competitive, it was necessary to reduce their capital costs by 10%, achieving a scenario with less installed fossil capacity.

Figure 2. Installed capacity from 2021-2050 by technology.

Figure 3 shows the evolution of electricity generation by technology from 2021 to 2050. Until 2030, there is no participation of fossil-based generation, with electricity imports complementing generation to meet the increasing demand. By 2050, in the TR scenario, hydroelectric generation predominates due to its high generation capacity, while in the WS and WS+GCB scenarios, the water resource is reduced to 25%, leading to greater use of wind generation. However, in 2040 and 2050, an increase in the participation of fossil-based technologies is observed, especially in the WS scenario, reflecting the need for backup technologies due to water limitations.

Figure 3. Electricity generation from 2021 to 2050 by technology.

In the WS+GCB scenario, the reduction in hydroelectric resources decreases generation capacity to 25% due to water scarcity, driving the use of batteries as a key technology to manage system intermittency. These batteries store surplus renewable generation, especially during periods of high wind availability, and release energy during periods of low renewable generation or during peak consumption. Their integration enhances system reliability by providing an efficient solution to balance generation and consumption. Additionally, they help stabilize the supply and reduce reliance on fossil technologies as backup, promoting a more robust and sustainable energy system.

Figure 4. Battery storage capacity.

Figure 5 shows that annual CO₂ emissions are similar across scenarios, as the reduction in hydroelectric generation is mainly offset by an increase in wind generation. In 2050, the largest difference is observed: the WS scenario shows a 3.5% increase in emissions compared to the Trend scenario, while WS+GCB, thanks to the integration of batteries and a lower share of fossil technologies, shows a more moderate increase of only 0.56%. This highlights the importance of incorporating energy storage and renewable technologies to reduce dependence on fossil fuels, achieving a more sustainable system with lower long-term emissions.

Figure 5. Total annual emissions

Figure 6 shows the evolution of total costs by scenario, where it can be observed that, in the early years, costs are similar across the three scenarios. However, by 2030, the Trend scenario shows a more marked increase, reflecting the calibrated generation profile that enforces a specific trend for the country. Starting in 2035, costs begin to differ significantly, being higher in the WS scenario due to the gradual reduction in hydroelectric generation, which forces greater reliance on fossil technologies and other more expensive sources. In the WS+GCB scenario, total costs are moderated thanks to a 10% reduction in battery capital costs, facilitating the integration of energy storage.

Figure 6. Total costs

Discussion

Prioritize investments in variable renewable energy:

National authorities should focus their efforts on expanding the installed capacity of renewable generation technologies, particularly wind and solar. According to the results obtained in the scenarios evaluated in this study, wind generation stands out as the main generation technology in situations of reduced water resources, due to its competitiveness and the abundance of resources in the country. The incorporation of these technologies helps mitigate the decrease in hydroelectric generation, stabilizing the energy matrix and maximizing system efficiency under adverse conditions.

Implement economic incentives to promote storage technologies:

It is crucial for the government to introduce economic incentives, such as subsidies, tariff reductions, and accessible financing schemes, to foster the development and adoption of energy storage technologies, such as grid-connected batteries. In scenarios like those analyzed under water scarcity conditions, batteries have proven to be an efficient solution by absorbing excess renewable generation during periods of high availability and releasing it during deficit periods or peak demand. This significantly reduces reliance on fossil technologies.

Ensure the reliability of the power system in extreme drought scenarios:

Given the limitations of water resources, especially during prolonged drought scenarios, it is essential to develop strategies to ensure the stability of the power system under adverse conditions. The analysis results showed that when water resources were reduced to 25% of their availability, the system relied on increased wind generation and the strategic use of batteries to balance supply and demand.

Model Improvements

One of the main challenges in advancing toward a 100% renewable energy system in Uruguay is the intermittency of resources such as wind and solar energy. Increasing the temporal resolution of the model by implementing more hourly intervals would allow for a more detailed capture of hourly profiles and the daily and seasonal fluctuations of renewable generation. This approach is particularly important for evaluating how the system responds to climate variability. Higher temporal resolution would facilitate more efficient planning for battery usage, enabling energy storage during surplus periods and its utilization during deficit periods.

Data Collection

Extending the analysis using longer historical climate data will enhance the robustness of simulations. So far, models have primarily relied on data from the 2021–2023 period. Expanding the historical timeframe would allow for the inclusion of records from years

with extreme events, such as severe droughts or atypical wind seasons, thereby improving the model's ability to forecast and plan for future events. This would enable the projection of capacity factors that are more realistic and aligned with the country's conditions.

Another key aspect is analyzing updated technological costs based on the country's actual conditions. Reflecting these trends in the simulations is essential to evaluate the economic feasibility of Uruguay's energy system. Additionally, conducting sensitivity analyses on future costs will help project more realistic and sustainable scenarios, taking into account factors such as economies of scale and technological advancements.

Conclusion

The objective of this work was to evaluate the flexibility and sustainability of the Uruguayan electric system in its transition towards a 100% renewable model. Using the OSeMOSYS model, three scenarios were analyzed: a tendential scenario based on recent historical data, another with water scarcity to assess the system's response to hydroelectric generation limitations, and a third that incorporates grid-connected batteries to optimize supply and demand management. The results highlight the need to diversify the energy matrix, enhance storage capacity, and promote policies that ensure a resilient and sustainable system.

Although Uruguay has made significant progress toward a renewable energy system, achieving 100% still requires implementing solutions such as energy storage and a greater variety of sources. Batteries would allow the use of wind surpluses, stabilizing supply and reducing dependence on fossil fuels. However, challenges such as intermittency and high initial costs persist. In the three scenarios analyzed, fossil generation could not be completely eliminated, highlighting the need for greater flexibility and incentives.

In a scenario of water scarcity, the electrical system would rely more on wind generation and energy storage. Batteries would play a key role by storing energy during periods of high renewable generation, ensuring system stability during demand peaks. This would reduce the need for fossil fuel technologies, improving the system's sustainability and resilience.

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